

ASSESSMENT OF THE CURRENT STATUS OF TOURISM IN THE REGION AND THE FACTORS OF REGIONAL DEVELOPMENT OF POP DISTRICT

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Abstract. *The regional tourism industry, together with its various components and stakeholders involved in the development of regional tourism products and value chains, can be interpreted as an ecosystem. It unites all stakeholders, including government agencies and various business representatives. Approaches to determining the level of attractiveness for the formation of a tourism ecosystem based on an assessment of the region's tourism potential are the subject of research. The research methodology provides an algorithm for assessing the attractiveness of the formation of a tourism ecosystem by assessing the main indicators of regional tourism assessment. The purpose of the study is to develop strategic guidelines for increasing the efficiency of using tourism potential to form a regional ecosystem (the example of Namangan region). This article reveals the initial concepts of the theoretical foundations of the expansion and management of tourism infrastructure in mountainous regions.*

Keywords: *tourism infrastructure, "tourist landscape", attraction, landscape, ecological indicators, ecosystem, strategy.*

INTRODUCTION

The current tourism policy of the Republic of Uzbekistan and other countries, the impact of socio-economic factors, and the current state of global tourism, coupled with the increased demand for travel within the country, have become an impetus for the development of domestic tourism. Currently, the issues of managing the tourism industry in the Republic of Uzbekistan are becoming relevant in terms of finding optimal organizational and management approaches and solutions. Undoubtedly, a well-structured, sustainable and competitive model is needed for its further development. The regional tourism industry, together with its various components and stakeholders involved in the development of regional tourism products and value chains, can be interpreted as an ecosystem. Therefore, it is appropriate to propose and improve ecosystem models to accelerate regional development.

In order to achieve a balance between the various components of tourism development, it is necessary to carefully consider and develop methodological and comprehensive approaches to assessing the conditions and prospects for using tourism as a factor forming a system that ensures the economic and social well-being of regions.

Research basis: effective use and development of regional tourism potential is a prerequisite for the formation and development of a tourism ecosystem in this region.

Many studies have been devoted to the role of networks in the modern economy, but the issue of adapting such structures in the context of industrial development is currently very poorly studied.

Theoretical analysis of the literature on the topic

When analyzing the scientific literature on the topic, in particular, B. Richard in his scientific works emphasizes the need to use a type of marketing that promotes the destination (city, town, region, country) in order to increase the number of visitors to it.[1] In the studies conducted by Nickerson N.P. et al., which are unusually comprehensive in scope and depth, this introductory section of tourism provides a balanced coverage of all components of the tourism industry. It examines all aspects of private and public business related to tourism, such as theories, planning, environmental issues, operations and the interrelationships between many tourism enterprises. [2], [3]. V.T. Middleton, Woeber K.W. discussed the importance of proper tourism marketing and systematic monitoring of management processes in the development of tourism in regions. [4], [5].

In modern literature on tourism development, it is important to involve various participants in the process of joint creation and implementation of tourism - consumers, government organizations, financial institutions, local communities, cultural institutions, etc. [6,7,8]. According to the research conducted by McDonald [7], current research does not take into account the complexity of the relationships between tourism industry participants in creating a tourist product. However, the process of forming a competitive range of tourist products in the region and stabilizing tourist flows depends on the effectiveness of this interaction. [8,9]. In this article, the author tried to present an ecosystem approach to managing and developing the tourism industry. The need to ensure the technological independence and superiority of the country makes it urgent to analyze and theoretically understand the impact of the development processes of digital platforms and ecosystems on the creation of new technologies and business models in the tourism industry. In modern realities, it is necessary to take into account the complexity of tourist products for effective management of the tourism industry. Therefore, it is appropriate to talk about competition not between individual enterprises, but between integrated business structures in the form of networks.

The ecosystem approach to tourism is particularly relevant due to the development of so-called sustainable tourism. According to [10], sustainable tourism is defined as “tourism that fully considers its current and future economic, social and environmental impacts, and meets the needs of visitors, the industry, the environment and host communities”. It thus considers a multitude of interrelated actors, which makes an ecosystem perspective essential for understanding tourism in this context. It is tourism that allows regions to fully implement and support sustainable development processes in three main directions: economic (ensuring local income and creating new jobs), social (assuming the preservation of traditional and cultural practices familiar to local populations), and ecological (allowing the conservation and enhancement of existing resources of the natural environment).

Analysis and results

In the process of assessing the factors of territorial development of Pop district and the current state of tourism in the region, it is appropriate to comment on the following. Pop district accounts for 43.8% of the area of Namangan region, 9% of its population and the main part of its pastures. Industry plays an important role in the economy of the district. The main sectors in the district are construction materials, light, cotton ginning, and food industries. There are 11 industrial enterprises in Pop district, including 3 joint ventures, an automobile enterprise, and other activities.

The district borders on Jalalabad region of the Republic of Kyrgyzstan to the north, Chust, Mingbulok districts of Namangan region to the east, Buvayda and Dangara districts of Fergana region to the south, Asht district of the Republic of Tajikistan to the west, and Akhangaron and

Bostanlyk districts of Tashkent region to the east. The length of the border is 344 km. It occupies the area from north to south from the Chatqol and Ku-rama ranges to the Central Fergana Plains. The area is 2.94 thousand km². The population is 231.3 thousand people, which is 9% of the population of Namangan region. The district has 1 city (Pop), and the villages of the city are Uygur, Margizor, Yangiyer, Yangiabad, Vodiy, Gurumsaroy, Pungon, Kirchin, Maydamillat, Batyr botka, Chiganoq, Kenagaz, Beshsori, Navruz, Iskovut, Sang Kaynama, Khujaabad, Toda, Khalqobod, Orom, Drujba, Chorkesar, Madaniyat, Parda Tursun, Kornos (Navba-hor, Oltinkon, Uygursoy, Khalqobod).

The district is located in the north of Fergana Valley, in the north-west of Namangan region, on the southern slopes of the Kurama mountain ranges and the Syrdarya oasis, in a geologically active zone. The relief consists of plains, hills and mountains, rising from south to north. In the south (in Karakalpak steppe) and in the Achchikkul massif, the altitude reaches 350–400 m, and in the north, in the Chatkal mountains, it reaches 4000–4500 m. The plains on both sides of Syrdarya are the main areas for farming.

The climate is hot, long summers, and relatively mild and short winters. Syrdarya, North Fergana and Okhunbobay canals flow through the district, Chodaksoy, Govasoy, Jabborsoy, Olmosoy, Uygursoy, Tuzliksoy, Ugrijarsoy, Selgasoy flow through the foothills, and Keng-Kulsoy, Sansalaksoy, Rezaksoy and other streams flow through the mountains. There are also lakes Kaznok and Tavot.

The soil and vegetation in the district change from south to north. In the Karakal Pak desert on the left bank of Syrdarya, saline soils are found among the shifting sands and sand dunes. The soil of the developed lands is light gray soils. Wild plants in these places include saxaul, izen, yantok, reed, yulgun and others. Meadow-swamp and dark gray soils are found in the estuaries of Syrdarya and other rivers. There are also salt marshes. Willow, turangil, yulgun, salt marsh, mint, koga and other plants grow here. Gravel and gravelly stones, brown soils are widespread in the adir zone. The plants are mainly ephemeral and ephemeroid. In the mountain zone, the surface of the earth is covered with rocks and mountain meadow soils. Various trees and shrubs such as larch, juniper, mountain poplar, wild apple, hawthorn, as well as shirach, betaga, wormwood, isiriq and others grow here. Mountain pastures are widely used.

Economy. Industry plays an important role in the district's economy. The main industries in the district are construction materials, light industry, cotton ginning, and food industry.

Cotton cultivation is the leading agricultural sector. Grain, rice, fruit, viticulture, melon, vegetable, livestock, beekeeping, and cocoon farming also play an important role. The total irrigated area in Pop district is 39.3 thousand hectares, including about 31 thousand hectares of arable land, of which 16.3 thousand hectares are planted with cotton, 11.8 thousand hectares with grain, 245 hectares with potatoes, 471.5 hectares with vegetables, 154 hectares with melons, and 1922 hectares with fodder crops.

In the collective and private farms of the district, about 28.4 thousand cattle (including 12 thousand cows), about 59.4 thousand sheep and goats, more than 9.5 thousand poultry, 336 horses are kept (2002). The length of the collector-drainage networks in the district is 778.2 km. In the 2002/03 academic year, 39.5 thousand students studied in 38 general education schools, 800 students in 2 academic lyceums, and about 2 thousand students in 5 vocational colleges. There are 40 public libraries (book fund шы 504.7 thousand works), 17 clubs, 3 stadiums, 3 swimming pools, and 35 gyms in the district. There are 111 physical education teams, 44.2 thousand people regularly

engage in sports. There are 11 hospitals (810 beds), 23 outpatient clinics and polyclinics, 27 pharmacies, 2 paramedical and obstetric stations, and 16 rural medical stations, employing 324 doctors (20.9 doctors per 10,000 people) and 1,652 secondary medical workers.

Figure 1. Key factors of tourism potential in Pop district regional ecosystem

The total population of Namangan region in 2023 will be 3172.0 thousand people. Currently, there are 1051 tourism objects in Namangan region, 274 of them are cultural heritage objects, 27 are entertainment tourism objects, 35 are medical tourism objects, 38 are restaurants, and 677 are accommodation facilities. (See Table 1)

Table 1.

Factors of tourism development of Namangan region

№	Naming	Quantity (pieces)
1.	Total tourism facilities	1051
2.	Cultural heritage sites	274
3.	Entertainment tourism facilities	27
4.	Medical tourism facilities	35
5.	Total number of placement tools	677
6.	Tourist organizations (tour operator)	37
7.	Family guest houses	588
8.	Number of rounds	99
9.	Hostels	18
10.	Capacity coverage of seats in the total placement vehicle	10707
11.	Medical tourism facilities	35

1-the data table for settlements in Bugung Kund region has a total of 677 traffic lanes, and in 2023 it has 83 traffic lanes in Kuzbass. In Bugung Kund region in 2023, 64 out of 640 modern tourism hostels were organized according to the standards of a family guest and 10 out of 380 modern tourism hostels. The tourist organization (tour operator) consists of 37 people. The region has 588 family guests, 18 hostels, 99 travel agencies.

The studies were studied and it was found that there are the following problems in the field:
 - insufficient financial support for enterprising entrepreneurs in the construction and repair of small accommodation facilities (family guest houses, hostels, etc.).

- for the initiators who want to organize special accommodation facilities in the field of tourism at the expense of preferential loans, it is appropriate to attach a specific commercial bank

in each region and direct the credit resources only to projects in the development of the tourism sector.

- allocating bank loans in the process of launching the project of establishing various health centers in the district;
- it is necessary to establish modern business centers.
- development of viticulture (eco-agrotourism) in Chust district of the region;

Table 2.

Locating tools

№	Naming of placeholders	number	Number of seats
1.	Number of hotels	25	1560
2.	Hostels	18	1281
3.	Family guest houses	588	5880
4.	Hostel	6	244
5.	Sanatoriums	9	1039
6.	Resorts	4	410
7.	Campings	1	16
8.	Clinics	27	1269

Conclusions and suggestions

1. The region has high tourism potential and repairs roads leading to tourist attractions;
2. The construction of a new tourist destination by reconstructing water bodies located in this area, creating a complex including water attractions and partially creating a water body (beach);
3. It is necessary to form a targeted list of roads leading to tourist destinations in the Imam Ota, Gulistan and Kushminor rural municipalities of Pop district for the purpose of reconstruction and modernization;

The process of managing the tourism industry should be carried out taking into account the interests of consumers of tourist products and consumer behavioral trends. Its ultimate goal is to develop tourism in specific tourist areas and participate in the development, implementation and promotion of tourist products, taking into account the interests of individual industry participants (tour operators and travel agencies, accommodation facilities, catering establishments, transport enterprises, cultural institutions, etc.) that make up the regional tourism ecosystem.

In conclusion, the analysis identified strategies (institutional; business image; cultural and educational; innovation and technology) that determine the main directions of developing the tourism potential of Pop district.

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